

Interactive/Smart Whiteboard and Student-Teachers Academic Performance in Educational Technology at the University of Calabar, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of the use of interactive or smart whiteboard on student teachers' academic performance in educational technology. Two objectives, research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A non-randomized pre-test post- test experimental design was adopted with a total of 110 second year educational technology students as sample. Educational Technology Performance Test (ETPT) with a reliability co-efficient of 0.75 obtained from Kuder Richardson formula 21 was used in generating data for the study, Descriptive statistics of Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Covariance were used in analysis of data. Findings from the study showed that the use of interactive whiteboard was more effective in enhancing students' performance than the traditional whiteboard. The result also showed that there was no significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students who used the Smart board. Based on the research findings it was recommended that university managements should be encouraged to install Interactive whiteboards in classrooms and teachers should be sent on training on the use of these smart boards for instructional delivery.

Keywords: *Interactive/ Smart Whiteboard, Academic Performance, educational Technology.*

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Introduction

The education system is changing drastically globally, Nigeria as the 'giant of Africa' cannot be left out in this scheme of changes. Technology is becoming more and more vital in our world of today. Following this trend, technology within the education system is increasing drastically. Teachers and educators need to be ready and willing to

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embrace this change with effective and efficient instructional delivery in order for education to be meaningful, relevant and a means of solving societal problems.

Integrating technology into the teaching and learning process has become an acceptable best practice in the classroom setting. More and more teachers and educators are making efforts to differentiate instruction through the use of technology as key resources.

Polin (2015) in support of technological integration within the classroom asserts that computer- based technology has become the essential in- gradient in restructuring learning because it can provide the diversity in instructional methods necessary to reach all school children.

When technology is effectively used in the teaching process, the value of the lesson becomes priceless as teacher-student, student-material, and student -student interactions are enhanced. This increased interactivity changes the roles of the students and teachers, as the teaching and learning process becomes more collaborative and an integrated approach. (Miller, Glower & Averis 2023). Furthermore intrinsic motivations of students to learn is increased, an increase in students' motivation to learn, results in an increase in academic performance (levy, 2022). Studies have also shown that interactive whiteboard lessons are more student centered than traditional methods (Painter, Whiting & Wolters 2015).

Gender issues and academic performance of students in sciences has become a recurring decimal in educational studies and research. Research findings in the past reported the dominance of male in achievement especially in sciences. In contrast to this some studies reported that female students are academically better than male students in social sciences (Gammie, Gammie & Duneam 2023). There are also a number of research studies which revealed that gender has no effect on academic performance of students in mathematics and science (Ifamuyiwa & Akinsola, 2018). In Nigeria the integration of ICT tools in the science classroom is faced with several challenges even with the intervention of pilot schemes of the Federal Government in the Federal Government colleges in 1987, the story has not changed. In Akwa Ibom State for example the availability and usability of IWB is still an issue though some private schools, Federal Government colleges and universities have already integrated this technology in their classrooms. The traditional approach of expository and note taking is gradually losing its effects as technology is advancing in the educational system. One of the recent entrances of technology into the classroom setting is the Smart board or interactive whiteboards. These whiteboards based on computer technologies is fast replacing the traditional whiteboards.

An interactive whiteboard also referred to as smart board is a piece of hardware that looks much like a standard white board, but it connects to a computer and a projector in the classroom to make a very powerful technological tool. The interactive Whiteboard becomes a giant, touch-sensitive version of the computer screen. Instead of using the mouse, the computer is controlled through the interactive whiteboard screen just by touching it with a special pen. Anything that can be accessed from your computer can be accessed and displayed on the interactive whiteboard. For example word documents, power point presentations photographs, video clips, websites or online materials. Special soft wares in various subject areas are also included within the interactive whiteboard. With this one can interact with images and text projected on the board: clone, color, label, rearrange and change their sizes.

Wall (2015) went out to gather the opinions of primary school pupils about interactive whiteboards and to identify the effects of these tools on teaching and learning. The students listed benefits such as, easier comprehension, higher concentration, improved students' participation, more effective presentation of information, aiding memory. They also added that interactive whiteboards had more positive effects in mathematics and science classrooms when compared to the English class.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of the use of interactive whiteboard on students' academic performance in educational technology. The study seeks to achieve the following objectives.

To determine the effect of the use of interactive white board on students' academic performance in educational technology.

To determine if there is a difference in the academic performance of male and female educational technology students taught with interactive whiteboard.

Research Questions

1. How does the use of interactive whiteboard affect the academic performance of students in educational technology?
2. What difference exists between the academic performance of male and female educational technology students taught with the interactive whiteboard?

Materials and Method

The study adopted a non-randomized pre-test, post- test experimental design. The study covered all the educational technology students in the Faculty of Education University of Calabar during the 2021/ 2022 school year. The total population was two thousand one hundred and four (2,104).

Using purposive sampling technique, a sample of 110 students consisting of 56 boys and 54 girls from two intact departments offering the course: Educational technology in the second year of study in the Faculty of Education were used for the study. Each of the department was assigned as control and experimental group. One researcher's made instrument Educational Technology Performance Test (ETPT) was used for data collection. The ETPT consisted of 25 multiple choice questions constructed on the topic Microteaching process. The test was used to determine the performance of the student- teachers on the concept of microteaching.

The instrument was submitted for face and content validation by a computer scientist and one expert in educational technology. To ensure the reliability of the 25 multiple choice test items, results obtained from a trial testing group of 20 students was subjected to Kuder Richardson Formula 21 and a reliability co-efficient of 0.75 was obtained.

Educational technology teachers engaged in the facilitation of the course for year two students during the academic session served as research assistants. The researcher prepared a power point lesson package on microteaching process. Colorful internet diagrams of the components of microteaching process were also incorporated into the package. Pre-test was given to the two groups at the same time and the result obtained. The control group was taught with expository method using the conventional whiteboard while the experimental group was taught with the interactive whiteboard

using the lesson package developed by the researchers. A post test was administered for 20 minutes one week after the treatment. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of Mean, Standard Deviation, while the hypotheses were tested with Analysis of Covariance at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: How does the use of interactive whiteboard affect the academic performance of educational technology students?

Table 1. Adjusted Mean Scores of Students Taught Using Interactive Whiteboard and Those Taught Without

Strategy	N	Pre-test \bar{X}	Post-test \bar{X}	SD	Mean gain
Using Interactive Board	57	9.88	15.37	0.57	5.49
Using Non-Interactive Board	53	12.87	14.28	0.61	1.42

As shown in table 1, the adjusted mean of students that were taught using interactive board is 15.37 while those taught using non interactive board is 14.28. This implies that the adjusted mean score of students taught using interactive board is greater than that of those taught using non interactive. This is as illustrated in figure 1. In order to determine if the difference is significant, the scores were subjected to the Analysis of Covariance.

Figure 1. Graphical Illustration of Students' Academic Performance Based on Strategy

Research Question 2: What difference exists in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught using interactive whiteboard?

Table 2. Adjusted Mean Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Using Interactive Whiteboard

Gender	N	Pre-test \bar{X}	Post-test \bar{X}	SD	Mean gain
Male	28	10.14	15.21	0.15	5.07
Female	29	10.13	15.52	0.15	5.39

As showed in table 2, the adjusted mean of male students taught using interactive board is 15.21 while that of female students taught using interactive board is 15.52. This implies that adjusted mean score of female students taught using interactive board is greater than that of male students. This is illustrated in figure 2. shown below. In order to determine if the difference is significant, the scores were subjected to the Analysis of Covariance.

Figure 2. Adjusted Mean Score of Male and Female Students Taught Using Interactive Board

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of educational technology students taught using interactive whiteboard and those taught with whiteboard.

Table3.Covariance Analysis (ANCOVA) of Posttest Scores of Students Taught Using Interactive Whiteboard and those Taught Without

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign @ p<.0	Decision
Pre-test	31.88	1	31.88	3.96	.049	*
Main effects Interact	38.00	1	38.00	4.73	.032	*
Model	69.88	2	34.94	4.34	.015	*
Residual	860.50	107	8.04			
Total	930.37	109	8.54			

Note: *=Significant at P<0.05 alpha

As shown in Table 3, the calculated P-value.032 of the main effects of strategy is less than the alpha level. 0.5 .Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there exists significant difference in the mean performance scores of educational technology students taught using interactive whiteboard and those taught using interactive whiteboard and those taught without.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of male and female educational technology students taught using interactive whiteboard.

Table 4. Covariance Analysis (ANCOVA) of Posttest Score of Student Taught Using Interactive Whiteboard and those Taught Without

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign @ p<.0	Decision
Pre-test	.096	1	.096	.015	.905	NS

Main effects Interact	1.289	1	1.289	.196	.660	NS
Model	1.384	2	.692	.105	.900	NS
Residual	355.879	54	6.590			
Total	357.263	56	6.380			

Note: NS=Not Significant at $P < 0.05$ alpha

As shown in table 4, the calculated P-value. 660 of the main effect of strategy are greater than the alpha level 0.5. Therefore, null hypothesis is retained. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female educational technology students taught using interactive whiteboard

Discussion

This study investigated the effect of interactive whiteboard on students' academic performance in educational technology. The result as shown in tables 1 and 3 in terms of utilization of interactive board and academic achievement shows that there exists a significant difference in the academic performance of students. Those taught with IWB, performed better than those taught without IWB. These findings may be due to increased motivation and interest to learn as students were allowed to interact with the whiteboard.

This finding supports those of levy (2022) who noted that positive gains were realized in literacy, mathematics and science for children age 7-11. The research findings is also in line with Zittce (2019) who reported that students taught geometry with interactive whiteboard out performed those taught with traditional method. However this finding is at variance with Higgins, Beachamp & Miller (2017) who after a two year study found no significant difference in test scores between students in school using IWB.

Another area of concern of this study was to find out the effect of gender on students' academic performance when taught with IWB. The results on tables 2 and 4 indicated that the adjusted mean score of male students taught using IWB is greater than that of females; however the difference was not significant. This finding is consistent with the studies of Kost, Pollock and Finkelstain (2019), Ifamuyina and Akinsola (2018) and Gambari (2020) who revealed that there is no significant difference in performance of male and female students in mathematics and physics concepts respectively.

Conclusion

The traditional approach to learning in today's rapidly advancing technological world is no longer playing a vital role in students learning and academic performance. Technological advances like the interactive whiteboard creates opportunities for students to interact with learning materials thereby enhancing students' performance. The use of the IWB also does not seem to discriminate against gender.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Interactive white board or smart board should be installed in the lecture classrooms, in view of its stimulating and positive effect on students' academic performance.

2. Universities' Managements should invest in this technology and teachers should be sent for training in operational efficiency of the technology.
3. Educational technology teachers in particular and teachers generally should adopt strategies that make their lessons interesting, interacting and stimulating to students learning.

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